

The End of Science

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Hand in hand with the tides of civilization has been the search for knowledge about the world around us and how to better utilize its resources - science. The ages of our species are named - Babylon, Ancient Greece and Rome, Byzantium, Tang Dynasty, Middle Ages, Renaissance, and so through to the present. The growing role of knowledge in the development of civilizations is clear when it becomes apparent that labels for the most recent steps in development relate to science and its implementation. The Age of Discovery, The Enlightenment, The Scientific and Industrial Revolutions, The Machine Age and the present - The Information Age. At the end of all this we come to a time when knowledge is cheap, instantly available and essentially everywhere. Have we entered a new age where new science is an anachronism? What if the search for new knowledge is no longer valued or needed? Is this the end of science?

“Science” isn’t simply a static component running through the rise and fall of these civilizations. It too changed. A world borne upon superstition and myth gave way to a Scientific Method where empiricism was vital – there had to be evidence to support ideas. Furthermore, you had to test these against the wits of peers - you had to publish the work. It took Charles Darwin twenty years to gather his thoughts for the Origin of the Species. Publishing of science has evolved too. The eleven staff members at a mid-ranking NZ university chemistry department published 107 research papers in 2011.

Research papers, not that they are actually on paper much anymore, are currency for this proof of ideas. They are quanta that advance and challenge orthodoxy without taking things too far. The work represents a landmark, usually minor, in the relevant field. It may be years before the significance of any particular paper is realised, if at all.

What are these quanta? A research paper contains ideas held within reasonably constrained structure of introduction, methods, results, discussion and conclusion. In an ideal world, the end-result is a concise, reliable, validated element of knowledge that builds on what was known. What would a paper about the end of science look like?

I. Introduction - where the topic and approach are presented.

It is important to build a context for the reader and possibly, but not always, some motivation for the work. Having established the topic and line of enquiry, it is useful to pose questions or put forward hypotheses which the subsequent material then tests - the spine is described.

Knowledge can be lost as well as found. The least subtle form is, as seen again and again through history, a power-struggle that results in the wholesale murder of the thinkers. Alternately, it might be through war - such as the burning of the library in Alexandria. It might be the loss of socio-political will and resilience - the

giant pyramids of Egypt. It has happened in our lifetimes too – with the technobravery of manned lunar missions likely beyond us now.

Many of these backward steps have been driven by chosen responses to economic fortunes. As the effects of climate change start to become manifest, economies will be paying to rebuild and move cities away from the coast, away from drought, paying to make water. Money won't exactly be left lying about and science that doesn't immediately fix something will be harder to justify on the balance sheet – a knowledge squeeze. Ironically, the international scientific effort looking at the earth's climate system might have been exploring the driver of its own demise. Is this global feat of collaborative learning the last great scientific endeavour?

The hypothesis here is that the scientific era is taking its last gasp.

II. Methods - the techniques and protocols are described

This information allows readers to build their sense of trust in the results and, consequently, in the conclusions drawn. It also provides a basis for the work to be repeated – a fundamental component of the scientific method.

Science can mean different things to different groups of people, and different things to the same group at different times. Many might say they value science but then when told tabloid-like what some scientist is studying – “well, they didn't mean that sort of science”. It is important to define science for present purposes and here I define it as the search for new knowledge that is at least in-part investigator-driven, accepts risk in the outcome, the role of serendipity, the need for evidence and the chance of being wrong. Science also needs to be differentiated from technology. Whilst related, one is about ideas and the other is the manifestation of a small set of the first, plus a good deal of engineering and design. Further, there is feedback whereby technology changes how science works.

The Scientific Method seems self-evident nowadays, to the extent that one feels it must have always been so. It grew and developed to take ideas beyond reasoning based on myth, religion and superstition. This step, obvious to us, had to be taken by people who had no vision of their world from satellites, one where even James Cook had to find Tahiti using the moon and stars.

At a recent talk in Wellington, the Australian scientist and environmental figurehead Tim Flannery spoke of reductionism and ever-focusing science being not for him. And that, for him, climate science was a way of scaling back out to big-picture science. The challenge is that, in our finely balanced world, it appears that small things can manifest themselves in big changes. For example, tiny differences in the temperature of a particular current stream deep in the ocean causes ice to melt differently in some far flung corner of the poles, which in turn results in an ice shelf collapsing; an effect that forces 15 million people to abandon drowned cities. As it ever was, the devil is in the detail.

There is also a sense that we know it all and what we don't know we can model with a computer. From the perspective of an earth system scientist at least, it is ludicrous to think we know it all. It's close to the opposite. The more you know, the more you realise you don't know enough. Rather unsurprisingly, this globe of half a billion square km surface area, 7 billion humans, around 10 million other documented non-bacterial species, bathed with liquid, gas and solid water... turns out to be complicated.

III. Results - wherein the data collected are displayed

The data must be presented in sufficient detail so as to enable consideration of the veracity of the approach and connection with later material. But at the same time brevity is not only the soul of wit but a close personal friend of the editor.

It might be premature and pessimistic to see the end of science during a time of challenging economics – “it will bounce back once the economy recovers”. But the history of organised science is so short that we don’t have 20 examples of how such endeavour recovers after each and every economic depression. We don’t even know that the global economic situation will, or should, recover to its former state. Furthermore, the combination of civilisation and economy that emerges in the next decade will face successive waves of environmental change. Responding to this global-scale pressure will swallow up any discretionary spending and constrain endeavour.

New philanthropy is the same as the old philanthropy. An email arrived recently from my PhD advisor of two decades ago asking if I’d send him some money so he could support new PhDs. One I’d stopped laughing, I paused to consider the re-growth of philanthropy – private support of works for the good of humanity. It used to be the only way science got done. Joseph Banks was on the Endeavour when it passed beneath Venus on its day. His wealth was such that he paid for seven other scientists to accompany him on the voyage. The gap between this reality, only 10 or so generations previous to now, and the chance that I could personally afford to pay for colleagues and assistants to accompany me on field experiments is wide and deep. Science, in the sense of exploration of ideas and the unknown, was once a rich man’s game. What if it were to become so once more?

IV. Discussion - the results are considered in the light of the questions driving the work.

It’s time to face the “so what?” question. The results need to be placed in context, rationally dissected and generalised. The work should be related to other studies and clearly identified speculation made about where the information takes us. If the Introduction has been properly framed then this section should follow naturally.

But are things so different now? Ideas and the resources to explore them have always struggled to find support. Hence, the natural gravitation to government-run and funded institutes that brings a critical mass and some sense of security both to people and ideas. These structures develop sets of top-down goals designed, naturally enough, to justify their existence at the same time as meet the needs of their supporters. At its best this can lead to phenomenal achievements like the journey beyond our planet with the Apollo mission, or the search for the building blocks of the universe with the Large Hadron Collider.

Locally however, this top-down approach is found in a form known as Koru Lounge Science where a group of non-practitioners assemble and make decisions based on corporate and political pressures - the corporatization of science. This is life and one should get over it. But in actual science, the pathway between start and end is not necessarily known or even achievable. Koru Lounge Science struggles with this concept because it challenges its authority. The best path from Need A to Realisation B cannot be readily identified and the groups of minds best able to achieve the outcomes may not be the ones the Loungers were thinking of.

But change is upon us. The internet has acted as a catalyst for change in many aspects of civilization. For science, amongst many changes, it has thrown out challenges as to how discoveries are published. It is unlikely the accepted manner in which science is delivered will ever be perfect. The present system, at the same time as sorting wheat from chaff, makes the cutting edge of ideas struggle to prove themselves in what is essentially a conservative system. The internet is allowing both ends of the spectrum to evolve. It is now possible to get controversial but sound ideas out for all to see and to criticize. Whilst corners of academic publishing enable *possibly* dubious work to appear with the barest testing of its veracity. More than ever - *caveat emptor*.

The internet also provides tools with which to synthesize ideas. It might enable a thousand ideas (papers) to be galvanised into a new über-idea that brings something new to civilization. This has always been the case, but now this synthesis can be achieved rapidly and across divides never before crossed. We need to imagine things like Google Scholar and Wikipedia combined and stretched. Furthermore, we shouldn't simply imagine data mining tools that reach into some dark swamp of information. The science has to reach forward too, try and structure itself to accept this probing by making salient results and non-linearities as discoverable as possible. A taste of this is seen where Journals are beginning to list subsequent papers that cite the work you are reading – you are Dr Who travelling in space and time visiting the libraries of the planet. There will be skills in working in this new framework so as to best expose the work to the future. Different regional science systems will need to homogenize. The need for expert minds will actually increase as the automatically derived conclusions must be assessed, contextualised and re-questioned.

V. Conclusions - a distillation of the essentials of the work.

If nothing else, read this section (and the Bibliography - to see if you're listed). The author must distil the months and years of work to perhaps half a page of simplifications.

So what if it was the end of science? Would we know? Would we care? The real enemy of the future of science is cynicism. What if the scientific survivors of the knowledge squeeze were so cynical that the next big thing was a wry sneer? The cynicism would transfer to how funding was sought, the exploitation of students and how the public was engaged. It would contaminate the very act of asking questions. And science is all about asking questions - this document contains 16 question marks. This is normal, or should be. Science generates more questions than it answers. This can be frustrating for outsiders looking in – “but what's the answer?” Answers do exist but, except for the simplest of situations, there's usually a “but”. Perhaps this means its time to re-value the scientific currency. The answer to a big question might be found in a thousand papers. What is required is a tool to count this scientific currency and convert into higher denominations. Is this the big picture that Flannery was looking for?

It is typical in a paper to pull punches in case the author of the work you criticize ends up reviewing your work. So... it is likely that the end of science is not really the end – it just looks that way when viewed from within. Like some 1970s post-apocalyptic movie, will the end be a re-birth too? Dislocation of exploration from serious money and bureaucracy might enable a new class of science and scientist

to exist – the rise of the hobby scientists. Radical changes in computational power and communications will mean that science will go underground into networks of likeminded people. It's already doing this in lots of ways. It is not the end of science, but metamorphosis.

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